

Borate complexes in solution. Part-I. Equilibrium study on the mixed ligand complex formation of copper(II) with boric acid and (N,N) bidentate ligands[†]

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Combined pH-metric and spectrophotometric investigations on the mixed ligand complex formation equilibria of Cu^{II} with boric acid and (N,N) bidentate ligands, viz. bipyridine, 1,10-phenanthroline and ethylenediamine (hereafter, L) in 1 : 1 : 1 and 2 : 2 : 1 Cu^{II} : L : H₃BO₃ molar ratios reveal the formation of mixed ligand complexes of the types Cu(L)(H₂BO₄)⁻ and Cu₂(L)₂(BO₄)₄⁻. Formation constants of the complexes in aqueous solution at 25° and at a constant ionic strength, I = 0.1 M (NaNO₃) are determined and the complex formation equilibria elucidated on the basis of spaciation curves. Composition of the mixed ligand complexes formed in the solution has been confirmed by mole ratio method at I = 0.5 M (NaNO₃).

Acidity of boric acid is increased due to its complex formation with 1,2-*cis*-diols¹. Complexation equilibria of boric acid with *cis*-diols, *cis*-hydroxy acids, *cis*-dicarboxylic acids were studied by many workers². It is interesting to note that transition metal complexes having two coordinated OH groups or two H₂O ligands in *cis*-positions are structurally compatible to form such chelated complexes with boric acid as are formed between boric acid and 1,2-*cis*-diols. Although quite a large number of *cis*-diaquo and *cis*-dihydroxo metal complexes are known, till date there is no report of any study on the formation equilibria of complexes between boric acid and these complexes. In the present paper we describe the results of an equilibrium study on the complex formation of boric acid and (N,N) bidentate chelated 1 : 1, Cu^{II} complexes, Cu(L)²⁺, where, L = bipyridine (bipy), 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) and ethylenediamine (en). These complexes in aqueous solution are expected to have the right structural features like 1,2-*cis*-diols to form chelated structures with boric acid. The complex formation equilibria were studied by combined pH-metric and spectrophotometric methods at 25° in aqueous solution at constant ionic strengths, I = 0.1 and 0.5 M (NaNO₃).

Results and Discussion

Boric acid, H₃BO₃, gives a single buffer region in the pH-range 7.5–10.5 due to its ionisation, not as a Bronsted acid, but as a OH⁻ acceptor³,

In the presence of Cu(L)²⁺ complexes (L = bipy, phen, en),

the above buffer region is found to occur at lower pH-values, suggesting complex formation of H₃BO₃ with Cu(L)²⁺. Spaciation curves of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 Cu^{II} : L mixtures (L = bipy and phen) show that almost 100% of the total Cu^{II} remains in the form of Cu(L)²⁺ complexes at the very early stages of complex formation (pH ~ 2). pH titration curves of Cu^{II} in the absence and in the presence of boric acid show that the hydrolytic equilibria of Cu²⁺ (aq) ions and the complex formation equilibria of Cu²⁺ with H₃BO₃ are overlapping. Hence in calculating the formation constants of binary 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 Cu^{II}-H₃BO₃ complexes, the hydroxo species, Cu(OH)⁺, Cu(OH)₂, Cu(H₂BO₄)(OH)²⁻ have been considered in addition to the binary complexes Cu(H₂BO₄)⁻ and Cu(H₂BO₄)₂⁴⁻. In calculating the formation constants (Table 1) of the mixed ligand Cu^{II}-L-H₃BO₃ complexes with L = bipy and phen, such hydroxo species have been omitted, as 100% of total Cu^{II} in these systems also are found to be in the forms of Cu(L)²⁺ complexes at the start of titra-

Table 1. Formation constants* of mixed ligand copper-borate complexes in aqueous solution

Constant	Ligand (L)			
	H ₃ BO ₃	bipyH ₂ ²⁺	phenH ₂ ²⁺	enH ₂ ²⁺
pK ₂ ^H	–	1.32	1.90	7.10
pK ₁ ^H	9.00	4.23	4.96	9.89
log K _{Cu(L)} ^{Cu}	3.55	7.80	9.14	10.44
log K _{Cu(L)(borate)} ^{Cu}	–	10.97	11.60	12.10
log K _{Cu₂(L)₂(borate)} ^{Cu}	–	18.25	18.57	21.20

*Limit of error ±0.04 in log scale.

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Fig. 1 Speciation curves of Cu^{2+} /bipy/borate system (1) H_3BO_3 , (2) $\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})^{2+}$, (3) $\text{Cu}(\text{bipy})(\text{H}_2\text{BO}_4)^-$, (4) $\text{Cu}_2(\text{bipy})_2(\text{BO}_4)^-$, (5) $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{BO}_4)^-$

Fig. 2 Speciation curves of Cu^{2+} /phen/borate system (1) H_3BO_3 , (2) $\text{Cu}(\text{phen})^{2+}$, (3) $\text{Cu}(\text{phen})(\text{H}_2\text{BO}_4)^-$, (4) $\text{Cu}_2(\text{phen})_2(\text{BO}_4)^-$, (5) $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{BO}_4)^-$

tions ($\text{pH} \sim 2$) (Fig. 1). Concentrations of the hydroxo complexes, $\text{Cu}(\text{L})(\text{OH})^+$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{L})(\text{OH})_2$ are found to be negligible in comparison to the concentrations of the other species. Therefore, following species have been considered to exist in the complexation equilibria in the final calculation : $\text{Cu}(\text{L})^{2+}$, H_3BO_3 , $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{BO}_4)^-$, $\text{Cu}(\text{L})(\text{H}_2\text{BO}_4)^-$ and $\text{Cu}_2(\text{L})_2(\text{BO}_4)^-$. The relative proportions of the binuclear species, $\text{Cu}_2(\text{L})_2(\text{BO}_4)^-$ are found to increase in going from the 1 : 1 : 1 to the 2 : 2 : 1 molar ratio of Cu^{II} : L : H_3BO_3 . With the mixed ligand Cu^{II} -en- H_3BO_3 system, however, a small amount of Cu^{II} ion persists at the start of the titration. Therefore, all the possible binary and ternary hydroxo complexes as described above have been considered to exist in addition to the usual binary and ternary complexes in the calculation of this system.

The concentration profiles of H_3BO_3 , $\text{Cu}(\text{L})^{2+}$ and the mononuclear ternary $(\text{L})\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{BO}_4)^-$ complexes in the 1 : 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : L : H_3BO_3 systems with L = bipy and phen (Figs. 1 and 2) indicate the formation of the ternary complexes according to equilibria (2),

Speciation curves of the corresponding complexes with L = en (Fig. 3), however, indicate the equilibria (3),

In the 2 : 2 : 1 Cu^{II} : L : H_3BO_3 systems, the binuclear

Fig. 3 Speciation curves of Cu^{2+} /en/borate system (1) H_3BO_3 , (2) enH_2^{2+} , (3) $\text{Cu}(\text{en})(\text{H}_2\text{BO}_4)^-$, (4) $\text{Cu}_2(\text{en})_2(\text{BO}_4)^-$, (5) $\text{Cu}(\text{H}_2\text{BO}_4)^-$

mixed ligand borate complexes, $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{L})_2(\text{BO}_4)]^-$, are found to be the predominant Cu^{2+} containing species at $\text{pH} > 4.5$. In the 2 : 2 : 1 Cu^{II} : bipy : H_3BO_3 system, the 2 : 2 : 1 complex is predominantly formed at lower pH values as compared to the corresponding 1 : 1 : 1 complex (Fig. 1). In this system the formation of the binuclear mixed ligand complex may be described according to equilibria (4),

In the 2 : 2 : 1 Cu^{II} : (L=phen/en) : H₃BO₃ systems, the evidences of formation of the 2 : 2 : 1 complexes from the corresponding 1 : 1 : 1 complexes are, however, very clear (Figs. 2 and 3). The formation of binuclear Cu^{II} : L : H₃BO₃ complexes from the corresponding mononuclear ones with L = phen and en, may be described according to equilibria (5) and (6), respectively,

Electronic spectra of 1:1 Cu^{II}:L and 2:2:1 Cu^{II}:L:H₃BO₃ mixtures with L = bipy, phen and en at different pH values have been recorded. The electronic spectral curves of both the mixtures corresponding to the concentration maxima of Cu(L)²⁺ and Cu₂(L)₂(BO₄)⁻ complexes indicate a slight

Table 2. Electronic spectral data of 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : L and 2 : 2 : 1 Cu^{II} : L : H₃BO₃ mixtures at different pH

L	pH	λ _{max} (nm)	
		Cu ²⁺ : L (1 : 1)	Cu ²⁺ : L : H ₃ BO ₃ (2 : 2 : 1)
bipy	2.00	703	703
	2.60	701	702
	4.00	702	694
phen	2.00	711	711
	3.50	703	707
	6.00	676	665
en	2.00	811	811
	3.60	713	729
	5.50	686	673

blue-shift of the absorption maxima of Cu^{II} by about 10–15 nm in going from Cu(L)²⁺ to Cu₂(L)₂(BO₄)⁻ stoichiometry (Table 2), which may be supposed to be due to borate coordination to Cu(L)²⁺. The λ_{max} values (600–700 nm) are indicative of distorted octahedral geometry of Cu^{II} in these complexes³, in which each Cu^{II} ion may be equatorially coordinated by the two N atoms of the L ligands and two O atoms of the borate group, i.e. (HO)₂BO₂³⁻ in the mono-

nuclear Cu(L)(H₂BO₄)⁻ complexes (I) and the bridging BO₄⁵⁻ group in the binuclear Cu₂L₂(BO₄)⁻ complexes (II). The axial positions may be coordinated by the solvent water molecules. The formation of the binuclear mixed ligand complexes, [Cu₂(L)₂(BO₄)]⁻, have been confirmed by mole-ratio plot of the ternary Cu^{II} : L : H₃BO₃ mixtures at pH values corresponding to the concentration maxima of [Cu₂(L)₂(BO₄)]⁻ complexes.

Experimental

Boric acid, bipyridine, 1,10-phenanthroline, copper nitrate, sodium nitrate and nitric acid were of A.R. quality. Ethylenediamine (A.R.) was purified by distillation and was converted into its nitrate salt, air-dried and analysed⁴. All the solutions were prepared in double-distilled CO₂-free water. Carbonate free NaOH (G.R.) solution⁵ was standardised against hydrazine sulphate (A.R.) using methyl red-methylene blue mixed indicator⁶. Cu^{II} nitrate solution was standardised by ion exchange separation combined with acid-base and complexometric EDTA titrations⁴.

pH was measured with a Systronics 335 pH-meter employing a special glass electrode in conjunction with a SCE. pK_w of water at the experimental temperature and the activity coefficients of hydrogen ion at the experimental ionic strengths were obtained from literature^{7,8}. Analytical concentrations of H⁺ ion at the different pH-meter readings were calculated according to the usual procedure⁹. Procedure for pH-metric titrations was the same as described by Irving and Rossotti¹⁰. For the determination of binary Cu²⁺-ligand stability constants, Cu^{II} : ligand ratios of 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 5 and 1 : 10 were used. For studying the mixed ligand complexation equilibria, the Cu^{II} : L : H₃BO₃ ratios were kept at 1 : 1 : 1 and 2 : 2 : 1. Formation constants were calculated with the aid of SCOGS program¹¹, run on a IBM 300GL personal computer. The constants were refined over several cycles of operation and the values corresponding to the minimum standard deviation (0.01 ml) in the titre were accepted. Complex formation equilibria were elucidated with the aid of the speciation curves. Electronic spectra of 1 : 1 Cu^{II} : L and 2 : 2 : 1 Cu^{II} : L : H₃BO₃ mixtures with L = bipy, phen and en in aqueous solution at different pH values (pH 2–6) were recorded using a Hitachi U-3501 spectrophotometer.

Compositions of the mixed ligand Cu^{II} : L : borate complexes formed in solution were determined spectrophotometrically by mole-ratio method¹² at pH values corresponding to the concentration maxima of the 2 : 2 : 1 Cu^{II} : L : borate complexes as indicated from the pH-metric measurements. A series of solutions were prepared by mixing vary-

(I)

(II)

ing amount of boric acid to a fixed amount of 1 : 1 Cu^{II} · L : mixtures, L = bipy, phen and en. pH of the solutions were adjusted to the pH of the maximum formation of the corresponding 2 : 2 : 1 Cu^{II} : L : borate complexes keeping the ionic strength fixed at $I = 0.5 M$ (NaNO₃). Absorbance of the solutions at the corresponding λ_{\max} values were measured and plotted against the molar ratio of H₃BO₃/[Cu(L)]²⁺. Point of intersection at molar ratio of 0.5 indicated the formation of 2 : 2 : 1 Cu^{II} · L : borate complexes in solution.

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